

JHEAA

ISSN : 3032-1123

<https://doi.org/10.61796/ejheaa.v1i7.728>**ANALYTICAL STUDY OF OSIS MANAGEMENT IN FORMING STUDENT CHARACTER AT MTSS DARUL AMAN ACEH BESAR DISTRICT****Suzanni**

STAI Tgk Chik Pante Kulu Banda Aceh, Indonesia

suzanni@pantekulu.ac.id

Received: May 22, 2024; Accepted: Jun 29, 2024; Published: Jul 09, 2024;

Abstract: MTs Darul Aman, Aceh Besar District is one of the schools or madrasas in Darussalam District which tries to shape student character, both through classroom learning and through the OSIS. The OSIS of MTs Darul Aman, Aceh Besar District, has many programs, but it requires the cooperation of good teachers and management to develop OSIS members so that they have good character. This research is qualitative in nature. Qualitative research is a research procedure with descriptive data results. In collecting data, researchers carried out observation, interviews and documentation studies. Observations were carried out by means of interviews and documentation studies. The interview guide used was in the form of open ended and probing questions . The documentation study in this research was carried out on various notes and documentation regarding profiles and backgrounds, data or documents related to OSIS management in shaping student character. OSIS planning in shaping student character. Every OSIS activity at MTs Darul Aman, Aceh Besar District, always begins with planning contained in the work program created by the OSIS management together with the guidance and guidance of the School Principal. The process is always carried out throughout the day. Because it is believed that a good process will produce what is expected to shape the student's character. Evaluations carried out by supervisory teachers help develop the management of the OSIS administrators. Starting from program planning to the evaluation process and helping to communicate funding sources for activities to the school principal. The student's character can be seen from every activity , does have a positive influence on students. Because for every activity, students are always given targets for change.

Keywords: Management, OSIS, Student Character

This is an open-access article under the [CC-BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) license**Introduction**

Facing environmental conditions that are always changing, there is no other wiser way for a leader than to understand the nature of change itself and prepare the right strategy to deal with it. Schools (as part of a social organization) do not escape the conditions as stated above, which means that if a school wants to survive , let alone develop, it is required to be responsive to various changes that occur and be able to respond correctly. One of the environmental conditions that can shape a student's character is school. The school becomes a place where students express their talents through the Intra-School Organization (hereinafter abbreviated as OSIS). OSIS is a forum for students, as prospective members of society and prospective citizens. An understanding of the basics of politics, organization and leadership among students needs to be instilled from an early age. This is important to

do considering that students are the young generation who are the foundation and hope of the nation in the future. Student organizations in the school environment need to be empowered to become organizations that are able to develop students' talents, leadership abilities and build student character.

Character education has long been a core part of the history of education itself. The birth of education can be said to be an attempt to revive spiritual ideals that had been lost by the wave of positivism pioneered by the French philosopher Auguste Comte. Forester rejected ideas that reduced human experience to a purely scientific form of life. The government has recognized the importance of building national character for a long time. This can be taken from the birth of Law Number 17 of 2007 concerning the National Long Term Development Plan (RPJPN) 2005-2025, and the instruction of the President of the Republic of Indonesia Number 1 of 2010 concerning Accelerating the Implementation of National Development Priorities for 2010 which is an important legal basis for government to build national character.

According to the 1945 Constitution, article 31 paragraph (3) states, "The government seeks and implements a national education system, which increases faith and piety as well as noble morals in order to make the nation's life more intelligent, which is regulated by law. Apart from that, it is also strengthened in Article 31 paragraph (5) which states, "The government is advancing science and technology by upholding religious values and national unity for the advancement of civilization and the welfare of mankind." The government is now determined to develop national character as one of the main focuses. national development (Maswardi, 2011: 45).

Character can also be interpreted as morals, so that national character is identical to national morals or national character. A nation with character is a nation that has morals and good manners, whereas a nation without character is a nation that has no or lacks morals or does not have standards of good norms and behavior. Thus, character education is a serious effort to understand, form, and foster ethical values, both for oneself and for all members of society or citizens as a whole (Zubaedi, 2011: 19).

As a complete religion, Islam already has clear rules regarding character education. In the Koran you will find many points of discussion about morals or character. Such as commands to do good (ihsan), and benevolence (al-birr), keep promises (al-wafa), be patient, honest, fear Allah SWT, give charity in the way of Allah, do justice, forgive in many verses in the Koran 'an. All of these are noble principles and character values that must be possessed by every Muslim person .

The implementation of character education in Islam is concluded in the personal character of the Prophet Muhammad. In the person of the Apostle, noble and great moral values were embedded. Character or morals have an important position and are considered to have a vital function in guiding people's lives. It is God who commands humans to do justice, namely to fulfill the obligation to do good and the best, to show compassion for His creation by staying in touch with them and abstaining from various forms of bad deeds that hurt others and harm others. Meanwhile, according to Law No. 20 of 2003, article 3 states that national education functions to develop abilities and form a dignified national character. There are 9 pillars of character education, including: 1). Love of God and all of his creation, 2). Responsibility, discipline and independence, 3). Honesty / trust and wisdom,

4). Respectful and polite, 5). Generous, likes to help and mutual cooperation/cooperation , 6). Confident, creative and hard working, 7). Leadership and justice, 8). Kind and humble and 9). Tolerance, peace and unity.

The formation of a student's character as a whole can be done at school. Apart from the transfer of knowledge from teachers to students, there is also the formation of a good mental personality as implied in the goal of national education, namely the formation of humans who are devoted to God Almighty. Seeing this, of course, the abilities possessed by students outside of academics are accommodated and developed as far as possible by the school through OSIS and extra-curricular activities.

According to initial observations, the students involved in the OSIS at MTs Darul Aman, Aceh Besar District have good character after attending training and serving as OSIS administrators at the school. This is evident from the change in attitude of the OSIS members. Researchers also interviewed one of the MTs Darul Aman teachers, Aceh Besar District. The teacher said that there were students who did not obey school rules. However, after the student was elected as a member of the OSIS, a change in attitude was seen in the student. The head of the OSIS of MTs Darul Aman, Aceh Besar District said, "We are here, every Saturday holding mental development activities, such as speech training, leadership and many other programs that will shape our character as students at MTs Darul Aman, Aceh Besar District.

According to the Head of MTs Darul Aman, Aceh Besar District, "In strengthening the personality of students at MTs Darul Aman, Aceh Besar District, in order to realize character values in accordance with national education goals, character education through student development activities is pursued, among others, in the form of activities: (1) Building faith and devotion to God Almighty; (2) Student Orientation Period (MOS); (3) Intra-School Student Organization (OSIS); (4) Enforcement of Manners and Rules for School Academic and Social Life; (5) Scouting; (6) Flag Ceremony; (7) School Health Business (UKS); (8) Youth Red Cross (PMR); (9) Drug Abuse Prevention Education; (10) Talent and Interest Development.

Methods

type of research is qualitative. Qualitative research is a type of research that produces discoveries that cannot be achieved using statistical procedures or other methods of quantification . Through qualitative research, researchers can get to know the subjects and feel what they experience in everyday life. According to this definition, qualitative research produces descriptive data so that it is detailed about the phenomenon being studied (Basrowi, 2002: 1). The selection of data sources is not based on emotional closeness, partners, etc. which can influence the objectivity of data acquisition, but is purely based on the interests of the problem and research objectives. As Moleong argues, informants are people chosen according to the importance of the problem and research objectives (Lexy, 2002: 135).

The characteristics of the data source in this research are seen from the priority of the object to obtain more objective information. The data source is divided into two parts, namely the primary data source , namely the OSIS supervisor at the school. What is meant by formal leader here is the principal who teaches at the elementary school studied by the author where the teacher is directly involved in improving student learning outcomes at the

school. Secondary data sources are supporting data related to this research, namely the students and teachers involved in coaching. In qualitative research, the main research instrument is the researcher. This means that researchers in data depend more on themselves. In other words, humans are the main instrument of research. Other instruments can be used as an extension of the researcher (Budiman, 2004: 144-145). Data analysis is a researcher's effort to understand what is behind the data and make complete information easy to understand and find general patterns that arise from the data. Data analysis can be carried out using two methods, namely quantitative and qualitative (Hanafi, 2014: 109).

The data that has been collected is analyzed descriptively qualitatively. Clearly, the data collected is analyzed inductively at any time during the research by processing empirical material, so that it can be simplified into a form that is easier to read, understand and interpret. Data is interpreted to look for meaning and implications of existing relationships. In qualitative data research, one of the models is the Miles and Huberman Model, namely qualitative data analysis is carried out interactively and takes place continuously from data collection in the field until it is finished, complete and saturated. The steps to be taken are: 1). data collection, 2). data reduction, 3). data display, and 4). conclusion (Milles & Huberman, 1984: 133).

The method used by researchers to test the validity of the data is the triangulation technique. Triangulation in credibility testing is defined as checking data from various sources in various ways and at various times. Thus, triangulation consists of source triangulation, data collection technique triangulation, and time. Source triangulation is carried out by checking data obtained from several sources. The data obtained from several sources is described, categorized, and finally agreement (member check) is requested to reach conclusions. Technical triangulation is carried out by checking data from the same source with different techniques. Time triangulation is related to time effectiveness. Data collected using interview techniques in the morning when the sources are still fresh and have not had many problems will provide valid data so that it is more credible. The triangulation process that researchers carry out is by do this continuously throughout the process of data collection and data analysis, until it is believed that there are no longer any differences, and there is nothing more that needs to be confirmed to the informant. Triangulation was also carried out by testing the researcher's understanding with the informant's understanding. To add input and criticism, researchers discuss the results of the data obtained with colleagues, which is called "peer examination through discussion". Next, data categorization was carried out based on the questions asked. Finally, an audit was carried out on each data, then the data was analyzed and interpreted.

Results and Discussion

Planning in shaping student character. Every OSIS activity at MTs Darul Aman, Aceh Besar District, always starts with planning contained in the work program created by the OSIS management together with the guidance and guidance of the School Principal. This work program is always oriented towards building student character, where this school has the principle that by forming character, academic achievement will follow. The program created is made at the beginning of the semester. Look at the potential and interests of

students. This is also intended so that students feel at home and want to carry out the program created together.

Planning is a number of activities that are determined in advance for carried out in a certain period in order to achieve that goal set. According to Bintoro Tjokroaminoto, planning is a process systematically prepare activities that will be carried out to achieve certain goals. Prajudi atmosurodirdjo, defines planning as calculation and determination of something that will be carried out in order to achieve it specific goals, who does it, when, where, and how do it. SP. Siagian defines planning as a whole process careful thinking and determination regarding things that will be done in the future in order to achieve the goals that have been achieved previously determined. Y. Dior argued that what is called planning is a process of preparing a set of decisions to be implemented on future time, which is directed to achieve certain goals (Siagian, 1997: 78).

From the definition above, it can be concluded that what is called planning are activities that will be carried out in the future to achieve goals. From here planning contains elements, namely: 1). a number of activities determined previously, 2). there is a process, 3). results to be achieved, 4). concerns the future at a certain time Planning cannot be separated from elements of implementation and supervision including monitoring, assessment and reporting. Supervision in planning can be carried out preventively and repressively.

The process is always carried out throughout the day. Because it is believed that a good process will produce what is expected to shape the student's character. Therefore, in the process, we emphasize the process of getting used to the values that are instilled. So that it becomes the student's personality. And in our principle it is not at issue where children receive education, but what is most important is how the process is carried out. Teachers guiding the OSIS MTs Darul Aman Aceh Besar District always work extra to empower the OSIS program in carrying out its programs. Because coaching teachers are a place of consultation for administrators. So, in the researcher's observations, the OSIS teacher at MTs Darul Aman, Aceh Besar District always maintains intensive communication with the administrators.

The actuating function is part of a group or organizational process that cannot be separated. The terms that can be grouped into this function are directing commanding, leading and coordinating (Tanthowi 1983: 74) . Because of the actuating action as mentioned above, this process also provides motivation, to provide movement and awareness of the basis of the work they do, namely towards the goals that have been set, accompanied by providing new motivations, guidance or direction, so that they can realize and arise the will to work diligently and well.

Guidance, according to Hadari Nawawi, means nurturing, guarding and advancing the organization through every person, both structurally and functionally, so that every activity cannot be separated from efforts to achieve goals. In reality, guidance activities can take the following form: 1). Give and explain orders, 2). Provide instructions for carrying

out activities , 3). Providing opportunities to improve knowledge, skills/aptitude and expertise to be more effective in carrying out various organizational activities, 4). Providing opportunities to participate and contribute energy and thoughts to advance the organization based on individual initiative and creativity and 5). Providing corrections so that each person carries out their duties efficiently (Nawawi, 1983: 36).

Evaluations carried out by supervisory teachers help develop the management of the OSIS administrators. Starting from program planning to the evaluation process and helping to communicate funding sources for activities to the school principal. Evaluation is carried out to look at weaknesses and programs that have been implemented in order to perfect program implementation to shape student character. Evaluation is carried out by providing a report which is carried out and discussed together. Evaluations are usually carried out every Monday after the flag ceremony is held. discuss them to find out to what extent the objectives of each program can be achieved. However, in general, the evaluation process is usually carried out at the end of the semester, to determine good plans and programs for the new semester. The reference for evaluation is of course the comparison between planning and the results that have been achieved. There are from the ministry of religion, education supervisor and school committee.

Supervision is an activity that ensures work is carried out can be carried out in accordance with the plans or objectives that have been established set. In other words, supervision is conducting an assessment As well as corrections so that what has been planned can be implemented correctly. According to Mudrick, supervision is a basic process that is Sensibility is still necessary no matter how complex and extensive an organization is. The basic process consists of three stages, namely: 1). determine implementation standards, 2). measurement of work implementation compared to standards and 3). determine the gap (deviation) between implementation and standards and plans. In the supervision process there are at least three phases that must be passed in this supervision, namely: 1). leaders must determine or set standards, 2). Evaluation and 3). corrective action , namely carrying out corrective action with the aim that the objectives of the supervision can be realized. Meanwhile, the main goal of this guardian is to make sure what happens what is planned becomes a reality or can be realized (Mudrick, 1991: 98).

Controlling is important because it is the final bridge in the functional chain of management activities. Control is one way for managers to find out whether organizational goals are achieved or not and why they are achieved or not achieved. Apart from that, controlling is a concept of controlling, monitoring the effectiveness of planning, organizing and leadership as well as making improvements when needed.

Student character can be seen from every activity , does have a positive influence on students. Because for every activity, students are always given targets for change. And this will be seen during the process of students with fellow students , students with teachers, and also students with parents and the community. Where students are able to see good characters in the process of their daily interactions in the school and community

environment. And changes in character also affect the way children learn. Character education is a system of instilling character values in school members which includes the components of knowledge, awareness or will, and actions to implement these values. both towards God Almighty, oneself, others, the environment and nationality. According to Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning National Education Article 1 Paragraph, namely:

Education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble morals, and the skills needed by themselves, society, nation and state (Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning National Education Article 1 Paragraph 1).

Adhering to the definition above, character education is a conscious and planned effort to build/form a unique personality for students, namely a good personality characterized by honesty, toughness, intelligence, caring, responsibility, hard work, never giving up, responsiveness, self-confidence . , likes to help, is able to compete, professional, sincere in working together, loves the country, trustworthy , disciplined, tolerant, obedient and other behaviors with noble character

Conclusion

OSIS planning in shaping student character. Every OSIS activity at MTs Darul Aman, Aceh Besar District, always begins with planning contained in the work program created by the OSIS management together with the guidance and guidance of the School Principal. The work program is always oriented towards building student character, where this school has the principle that by forming character, academic achievement will follow. The program created is made at the beginning of the semester. Look at the potential and interests of students. This is also intended so that students feel at home and want to carry out the program created together. The process is always carried out throughout the day. Because it is believed that a good process will produce what is expected to shape the student's character. Therefore, in the process, the school emphasizes the process of getting used to the values that are instilled. So that it becomes the student's personality. And this principle does not matter where students receive education, but what is most important is how the process is carried out there. Teachers guiding the OSIS MTs Darul Aman Aceh Besar District always work extra to empower the OSIS program in carrying out its programs. Because coaching teachers are a place of consultation for administrators. So, in the researcher's observations, the OSIS teacher at MTs Darul Aman, Aceh Besar District always maintains intensive communication with the administrators.

Evaluations carried out by supervisory teachers help develop the management of the OSIS administrators. Starting from program planning to the evaluation process and helping to communicate funding sources for activities to the school principal. Evaluation is carried out to look at weaknesses and programs that have been implemented in order to perfect program implementation to shape student character. Evaluation is carried out by providing a report which is carried out and discussed together. Evaluations are usually carried out every Monday after the flag ceremony. Deliberate to find out to what extent the goals of each program can be achieved. However, in general, the evaluation process is usually carried out at the end of the semester, to determine good plans and programs for the new semester. The reference for evaluation is of course the comparison between planning and the results that have been achieved. There are from the ministry of religion, education supervisor and school committee.

Student character can be seen from every activity , does have a positive influence on students. Because for every activity, students are always given targets for change. And this will be seen during the process of students with fellow students , students with teachers, and also students with parents and the community. Where students are able to see good characters in the process of their daily interactions in the school and community environment. And changes in character also affect the way children learn

References

- [1]. Amin, M. Maswardi. (2011). *Pendidikan Karakter Anak Bangsa*. Jakarta: Badouse Media.
- [2]. Basrowi, Sudikin. (2002). *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif Prespektif Mikro*, Surabaya: Insan Cendikia.
- [3]. Budiman, Aris. 2002). *Desain Penelitian, Pendekatan Kualitatif & Kuantitatif*, Jakarta: KIKI Press.
- [4]. Hanafi, Abdul Halim. (2014). *Metodologi Penelitian Kependidikan, Cetakan I*. Batusangkar: STAIN Batusangkar Press.
- [5]. Lexy J. Moleong. (2002). *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*, Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya,
- [6]. Milles, M.B. & Huberman, M.A. (1984). *Qualitative Data Analysis*. London: Sage Publication.
- [7]. Robert G. Mudrick, dkk, (1991), *Sistem Informasi untuk Manajemen Modern*, Jakarta: Erlangga.
- [8]. Siagian, Sondang P. (1997). *Sistem Informasi untuk Mengambil Keputusan*, Jakarta: Gunung Agung.
- [9]. Tanthowi, Jawahir. (1983). *Unsur-unsur Manajemen Menurut Ajaran Al-Qur'an*, Jakarta: Pustaka Al-Husna.
- [10]. Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia Nomor 20 Tahun 2003 Tentang Sistem Pendidikan Nasional Pasal 1 Ayat 1.
- [11]. Zubaedi. (2011). *Desain Pendidikan Karakter: Konsepsi dan Aplikasinya Dalam Lembaga Pendidikan*. Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media Group.